

Influence of Social Media on Kannada and English Literature Students

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ABSTRACT:

In the present study was conducted to examine the influence of social media on Kannada and English literature students. In recent decade's social media is very popular in Indian population especially in youths. Social media it refers to online platforms where the users can share and chat more information and connect with virtually to others through text message, video messages, photos, images and other content. It includes many types of apps or websites formed for messaging and chat, social platforms like WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, and TikTok etc. finally this study measure influence of social media on Kannada and English literature students. The sample for the study consisted of 50 Kannada and English literature students (25 Kannada literature students and 25 English literature students), aging between 22-25 years. The participants completed the Bergen social media addiction scale (BSMAS) developed by Andreassen et al. (2016). The obtained data was analyzed by using mean, SD and 't'-test. Further, Spearman's coefficient of correlation was applied. The result of the study concluded that there is no significant difference between influence of social media on Kannada and English literature students. Also, there is no significant relationship between Kannada and English postgraduate literature students

KEYWORDS:

Social Media, Kannada literature, English literature, Literature students.

Introduction:

The Social media there are various types and nature of work are an emerging and very powerful medium of communication. There are many types of communication. The Social media has emerged the fourth wave of communication after print media, radio, television (TV) and Theatre art. It brought tremendous changes among the people's lifestyles world over. To reach the population of 50 million families; many communication tool reach the people took the few years after discover but the Social/digital media took just 4 years. The emerging social media have brought about the death of distance due to its distinctive technology of surpassing time and geographical boundaries but at the same time various phenomenal changes among the socially human behaviors of the users especially of the age group 12–25 years. Computer and mobile phones are inevitable gadgets amidst Indian urban and rural Environment. The digital connectivity may lead in reducing the digital divide and means of communication among the Kannada and English medium adolescent users of social media. Every day the user of social media spends two hours and twenty-one minutes its average level. Each month all social media user visiting an average of 6.8 different social media platforms. These were the most widely used social media Facebook, 3.07 billion users. YouTube, 2.53 billion users. WhatsApp, 2 billion users. Instagram, 2 billion users. TikTok, 1.59 billion users. WeChat, 1.38 billion users. Telegram, 950 million users. Facebook Messenger, 947 million users. Snapchat, 850 million users. Douyin, 766 million users. as of 2025 February.

Literature is any and many collected of written work, but it is also used more narrowly for writings exactly considered to be an art form, especially novels, plays and poems etc. these are all consisting of both print and digitalized writing. In recent decades, this definition has enlarged to include oral literature, much of which has

been transformed. Literature is a method of recording, preserving and transmitting knowledge and entertainment. There is a psychological, social spiritual and political role are there.

Kannada and English literature students in Karnataka and globally involve with the distinct linguistic and cultural landscapes of both languages. Students of master degree in Kannada literature study the historical, social, and philosophical contexts of the language's extensive tradition, encompassing ancient epics and modern novels. Meanwhile, English literature students develop core language skills, foster critical thinking, and explore diverse literary works and trends. Universities and institutions, particularly in Karnataka, offer specialized programs for Kannada literature, often integrating it with other disciplines and research, while English literature programs focus on a broad understanding of global literary traditions and their impact on society.

Review of literature:

Kannada and English literature students use of many social media in their daily life. Adolescents and adults spend more time in social media, it problematic to self and others. Social media widely used of many situations its available in the toilet, bathroom, bedroom, temple etc. lot of concerns about youths and teenagers more depend on it to meet their emotional satisfaction. Kirk-Patrick C, Steijn R. (2014). Found that students use social media always may lot of changes in sleeping and waking daily habits, and be back school achievement. Furthermore, social media has one of the main reasons multiple adolescent problems like depression and insomnia. Shakya H B, Christakis N A (2017) and Panic I (2014) explored that social media addiction has the potential to negatively impact of adolescent and adult's life satisfaction. Many researches on social media sites use and mental health have shows that long-term use of

social media sites like Facebook is positively correlated with mental issues like stress, conflict, tension, anxiety, and depression, and negative effect on long-term happiness. Karpinski AC, et al (2013) investigate that there is a connection between some types of social media sites usage and very poor performance in academically. Take the help from professionals minimize social media addiction by develop and prepare the training for adolescents to help exist from its effects, and solve the problem of social media addiction.

Objectives of the study:

1. To assess the influence of social media on Kannada literature students.
2. To study the influence of social media on English literature students.
3. To know the correlation between Kannada and English literature postgraduate students.

Hypotheses:

1. There would be significant difference in the influence of social media on Kannada and English literature students
2. There would be significant correlation between influence of social media on Kannada and English literature students

METHOD:

Sample:

This research study sample of 50 they are all Kannada and English literature students from Kuvempu University campus, Shankaraghatta, Shivamogga. Karnataka state, India (25 Kannada literature students and 25 English literature students). The age of the samples is 22 to 25 years and they were selected from Kannada and English PG Center, Kuvempu University, Shivamogga. Karnataka

state, India.

Tools used for the Study:

Bergen social media addiction scale (BSMAS) developed by Andreassen et al. (2016). This is a 6 item self-report questionnaire that measure addiction of social media over the past year. It consist many areas such as salience, tolerance, mood modification, withdrawal, conflict, and relapse. Participants respond on a 5-point rating scale (1 = very rarely, 5 = very often), High score indicate high level of social media addiction low score indicate low level of social media addiction.

Data collection procedure:

The researcher took permission the respective authorities of both PG centers at Kuvempu University. Shivamogga, Karnataka state, India, for collecting data. Then investigator explained about the purpose of the tests to the sample and thus administered the test. After collecting the data, then questionnaires were scored as per the scoring pattern prescribed in the manuals.

Statistical analyses:

Mean, SD, 't' test and Spearman's coefficient of correlation is used for the data analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Table 1: shows the Mean, SD, and 't' value of overall social media addiction of Kannada and English literature students.

	Kannada literature students (N=25)		English literature students (N=25)		
Variable	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	t value
Social media addiction	50.42	11.27	49.16	10.98	1.19NS

NS- Not Significant at 0.05 levels

Table no-1 reveals the result of social media addiction of Kannada and English literature students. The overall social media addiction of Kannada and English literature students, Kannada literature students mean score=50.42, SD= 11.27. And the English literature students mean score= 49.16, SD= 10.98. The obtained 't' value is 1.19, which is not significant at 0.05 level. It means there is no significant difference between influence of social media on Kannada and English literature students.

Table 3: Shows Correlation between influence of social media on Kannada and English literature students

Variables	N	r	P
Kannada literature students	8	0.376	0.001NS
English literature students			

Not Significant at the 0.05 level

Table no -3 reveals that the Spearman correlation of influence of social media on Kannada and English literature students r value is 0.376, and the corresponding p-value is 0.001. And it is not significant at 0.05 level. Analysis of the table indicates that there is no significant correlation between influence of social media on Kannada and English literature students.

Conclusion:

1. There is no significant difference between influence of social media on Kannada and English literature students.
2. There is no significant relationship between influence of social media on Kannada and English literature students.

References:

1. Ahmed, S., & Singh, R. (2020). The impact of academic stress on student performance in higher education. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 45(2), 112–123. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000235>.
2. Barber, B. (2002). *Intrusive Parenting: How Psychological Control Affects Children and Adolescents*. Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.
3. Carol Ryff (1995) scale measuring psychological wellbeing.
4. Eraslan–Capan B. (2015) "Interpersonal sensitivity and problematic Facebook use in Turkish university students." *The Anthropologist* 21(3):395–403.
5. Glozah, F. N. (2013). Academic stress and perceived social support on the psychological wellbeing of adolescents in Ghana. *Open journal of medical psychology*, 2(4), 38258, 8.
6. Goody 1987.
7. Goody, Jack. "Oral literature". *Encyclopaedia Britannica*. Archived from the original on 14 December 2019. Retrieved 27 July 2020.; see also Homer.
8. Karpinski AC, Kirschner PA, Ozer I, Mellott JA, Ochwo P. (2013) "An exploration of social networking site use, multitasking, and academic performance among the United States and European university students." *Computers in Human Behavior* 29(3):1182–1192.
9. Kumaraswamy, N. (2013). Academic stress, anxiety and depression among college students A brief review. *International review of social sciences and humanities*. 5(1), 135–143.
10. Kirk–Patrick C, Steijn R. (2014). How much of an effect does social media have on insomnia and depression. Research Paper based on lectures at the Medlink Workshop Conferences at Nottingham University.
11. Marwan Zaid Bataineh (2013). Academic stress among undergraduate students: the case of education faculty at King Saud University. *International Interdisciplinary Journal of Education* – January 2013, Volume 2, Issue 1, 82–88.
12. Maurya, A. (2019). What are common characteristics of college students?

- Quora. Retrieved from <https://www.quora.com/What-are-common-characteristics-of-college-students>.
13. Monica Baiju and Dr. Rajalakshmi V R (2021) Academic Stress and Psychological Well-Being among College Students. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology* ISSN 2348-5396 (Online) | ISSN: 2349-3429 (Print) Volume 9, Issue 3.
 14. Munir, T., Shafiq, S., Ahmad, Z., & Khan, S. (2015). Impact of loneliness and academic stress on psychological well-being among college students. *Academic research international*, 6(2), 343-355.
 15. Oxford Learner's Dictionaries. Archived from the original on 10 June 2021. Retrieved 24 July 2020.
 16. Pantic I. (2014) Online social networking and mental health." *Cyberpsychology, Behavior, and Social Networking* 17(10):652-657.
 17. Rettberg, Scott (2019). *Electronic literature*. Cambridge, UK Medford, MA: Polity press. ISBN 978-1-5095-1677-3
 18. Shakya HB, Christakis NA (2017) "Association of Facebook use with compromised well-being: A longitudinal study." *American* 185(3):203-211.
 19. Toker S, Baturay M H (2016) "Antecedents and consequences of game addiction." *Computers in Human Behavior* 55:668-679.

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Conflict of interest:

The Authors have no conflict of interest to declare that they are relevant to the content of this article.

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